

Electoral Malpractices And Violence At The Polling Stations: Threat To The Conduct Of Future Elections In Nigeria

Rufus Aisedion¹, Joseph Osayande Akhimien², Omoregie Edoghgho³

¹Department of Political Science,

²Department of Sociology,

³Department of Political Science

Ambrose Alli University Ekpoma Edo State, Nigeria

Corresponding Author: Rufus Aisedion

ABSTRACT

Electoral malpractices and violence at the polling stations have generally been given low priority attention by disregarding polling units which are the primary stage where intimidations and various manipulations are carried out by greedy politicians and electoral staff. The perpetuation of ill electoral activities at the pooling stations has caused emotional disorder and psychological harm to the electorate and candidates. This is apparent because of the inadequacy in capacity building needed to engage the competence of electoral institutions, political parties, security agencies and the electorate in the electoral process. The study focuses on the threat electoral malpractices and violence at the polling units pose on the conduct of future elections. The paper employed qualitative method of research, sourced from textbooks, internet, journals among others, and comprehensively analyzed using historical analysis. The findings emphasized the inadequacy in capacity building in the electoral process and political institutions have made simple ways for overzealous politicians to perpetrate electoral malpractice and violence in Nigeria. It also revealed the collaborations between some INEC officials, party agents, candidates and some of their ardent supporters in the business of committing election malpractices and violence at the polling units. The findings also pointed out vote buying, intimidation of voters, unnecessary delay of voters, late arrival of electoral officials and their ad hoc staff, thuggery, padding of ballot papers, shooting of fire arms to scare away voters, among others. It is recommended that capacity building through mass education and the strengthening of institutions will reduce lack of knowledge of the electorate; promotes good governance to instill the consciousness to vote candidates of their choice.

Keywords: Electoral Malpractices, Election, Democracy, Violence, Polling Unit

INTRODUCTION

In a liberal democracy, political parties are the bedrocks for interest aggregation and platforms for fielding candidates for elections. Political parties also develop programmes of activities and manifestoes, and get the elected party members guided in the discharge of their responsibilities. Other function include: recruitment of members, selection and election of candidates during party primaries and presentation of those elected in the party primaries to compete with candidates of other political parties in general elections. In every election in Nigeria, whether intra or interparty, electoral malpractices and violence have always characterized the process. Thus, the subversion of democratic tenets has negative bearing on electoral integrity both in intraparty and interparty democratic processes. The problem is that capacity building in the electoral institutions is undermined which in turn generates electoral malpractices and violence in Nigeria. It is expected that capacity building can play a crucial role particularly to enhance and manage elections transparently for a smooth electoral process. It can also strengthen electoral institutions; empower

citizens, and enhance the overall integrity of the electoral process. It is believed also that capacity building can promote the rule of law and strengthen legal frameworks and judicial systems, which are crucial in addressing electoral malpractices.

Therefore, capacity building as it relates to electoral process refers to the capability to perform electoral functions efficiently and effectively to ensure free, fair and transparent elections in order to eliminate the possibility of electoral violence [1]. It is appropriate for voters to know their rights and be informed about electoral process through capacity building programs such as: Educating voters about their rights and the electoral process, empowering them to recognize and report malpractices, and discourage opportunities for malpractices and violence. From the historical and contemporary development of political parties in Nigeria, the structures, organogram, candidate recruitment exercise and decision making processes, are no doubt at variance with universal best practices [2]. In contemporary Nigeria, for example, the analysis of political parties indicates the following:

1. That they are not well structured, organized and managed
2. They pay less attention to membership mobilization and recruitment
3. They lack productive professional cadre staff
4. They fundamentally rely solely on 'moneybags' and 'god-fathers' for funding
5. Many operate in breach of electoral legal framework
6. They are undemocratically operated and managed
7. They are characterized by conflicts and violence both in intra-party and inter-party relations
8. They engage with the electoral process with a mindset of intimidation and harassment, vote buying, abuse of power and privilege, fraud, among others [2].

The above features are clear indicators of weak electoral processes with susceptibility to subvert democratic processes in Nigeria. According to Laden cited in Akanji (3), electoral violence means the act of inflicting voters and political opponents with dangerous weapons to cause bodily harm for the purpose of distorting the electoral process. This implies that electoral malpractice has to do with the emergence of leaders into political offices through undemocratic process, and whose motives are not to represent the interest of the people and the state. In recent times, electoral malpractice has discouraged the political participation of citizens making political apathy to be obvious. This was evident in the 2019 elections where most voters who turned out for the presidential election refused to turn out for the gubernatorial election. The reason was based on believe that their votes would not be counted or included during the collation of results [4]. Thus, any unregulated activity done to influence the electoral process with the determination to subvert the outcome of an election is electoral malpractice. Therefore, such practices include but not limited to the use of thugs, violently snatching of ballot, harassment of voters and political opponents, killing and maiming of the electorate and declaration of rigged election results.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Electoral Mal-practices

Any democratic process must involve elections and Nigeria being a democratic country has had series of elections marred with irregularities. For instance, the conduct of previous general elections such as 1999, 2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019 and 2023 in Nigeria were largely flawed by vote buying, underage voting, ballot boxes snatching and result manipulations [5]. This is why the fight for credible, free and fair elections was in front burner during the campaign of 2023 general elections. According to

Haruna, Okunola and Ocheme (6), electoral malpractices manifest as greed, lack of accountability and transparency. Others include: The promotion of personal interests, inducement and violence, vote buying and bribery of electoral and gullible voters with impunity. Past studies have succinctly articulated different categories, causes and consequences of electoral malpractices in Nigeria. According to Ugwuja (7); electoral malpractices on pre-election time, election period and post-election time.

Thus electoral malpractices are of three phases:

1. Manipulation of rules. This is the distortion of electoral laws to favour a particular candidate in an election. This is when names of eligible voters are intentionally excluded from voters' register to prevent them from voting during election.
2. Manipulation of voters. This is to distort electorate's choices. By employing deceptive tactics that violate campaign laws or being bias and lopsided in media coverage of the election. The other according to Isma'ila and Othman (8), is the change of choices at the polling station, through vote-buying, ethnic patronages, religious affiliation and intimidation to increase the vote of a favoured candidate or political party.
3. Manipulation of election results. This stage consists ballot-box stuffing, misreporting, deliberate short fall of voting facilities in opposition's places of strength, lack of transparency in the entire process of the elections, bias adjudication of electoral disputes in electoral tribunals.

Electoral Violence

Electoral violence according to Straus and Taylor (9), relates to direct physical violence such as assassinations or willful killings, destruction of opponents' vehicles and arson. Most times, violence starts by mere harassment and intimidation of party members and contestants, to disruption of election processes. This assertion only addressed the aspect of physical violence whereas physical harms alone do not fully define electoral violence. On this note, electoral violence can be defined as a fierce attack carried out with the aim of impacting the results of an election to favour a particular candidate against the other. It is an activity which causes harm and intimidation during election to influence the outcome of the election [10]. This is where civil society organizations need to be strengthened through capacity building. The reason is to be able to mobilize communities to advocate for fair elections and challenge electoral malpractices and violence. Furthermore, election violence has to do with electoral timing and motive. Timing which relates to

mayhem carried out during the election period, while the motive is tilted towards influencing the electoral outcome [11]. Electoral violence is an action directed at controlling the electoral processes to affect the results of the elections or by contending the legitimacy of the outcome of the electoral process [12]. It also connotes threat of harm against electoral process, persons and property during the election [13].

From the analyses, it is clear that election violence is a behaviour associated with the purpose of committing physical harm to affect electoral outcomes or the electoral procedure itself. However, there is post electoral violence which is not directed at changing the outcome of an election, but as an expression of disappointment of an election's outcome. Generally, any act that is capable of oppressing and impinging on a voter's or group of voters' rights or an act that inhibits the free choice of the electorate from participating in election is tantamount to electoral violence. The tendency for contestant to use available means at their disposal to win an election is hinged on the winner takes all syndromes. According to Diamond (14), many African states concentrate resources and power at the centre by turning politics into a zero-sum game which is the fundamental reason why political elites device fraudulent means to edge out opponents by any means.

Viewing past elections one cannot but establish that irregularities and violence have unavoidably distorted elections in large proportion. The Nigeria's 2023 elections, electorate particularly the youths were ready to vote in order to register their discontent over the social and economic problems facing them. These problems were distinctively identified such as disillusionment arising from government performance, unhealthy competition for resources, inter-and intra-ethnic distrust, unemployment, and lack of due process or rule of law. In a country like Nigeria, where attendance of appalling governance, communal disputes, and violence sponsored by selfish and self-serving politicians, the desires to cause mayhem and perpetuate self in power characterized 2023 general elections [15]. Given the above allusion, Nigerian politicians are persistently employing intimidation, violence, fraud, and corruption, as their weapons of winning elections. The manifestations of the above have denied Nigerian voters to freely elect their leaders in 2023 general elections.

In addition, the causes of electoral misconducts and violence in Nigerian elections have also been addressed by some researchers. For example, the causes include: Weak government institutions, lack of transparency, poverty and unemployment. Others are inadequate capacity building and political control over anti-corruption [16]. Further studies connote that

lack of political will and weak electoral laws in enforcing the rule of law exacerbate misconduct in Nigeria's democracy [17]. According to Haruna, Okunola and Ocheme (6), the implications of electoral misconducts and violence abound, for instance, elections mistrust is embedded, proficient candidates are rigged out from securing victory, among other things. According to Ebegbulem (18), irregularities in electoral process are often opposed with violent protests and litigations leading to ethno-religious politics, poverty and mismanagement of resources. According to Lawal (19), the process of electoral misconduct and violence, political parties are twisted and thereby lack the capacity to grow in their administration and structure thereby affecting sustainable democracy. Some scholars maintained that to gain access to political space in Nigeria, electoral misconduct is often used resulting in unstable economy, lack of accountability, transparency, quality service delivery, poverty, insecurity of lives and property, serious threat to peaceful coexistence, among others [20]; [21]. Other scholars like Isma'ila and Othman (8); Olurode (22), assert that electoral misconduct in Nigeria enhances the resources of few political office holders while the other citizens are impoverished and dehumanized.

Haruna (23), in his work "Analyzing electoral misconduct: The Case of 2019 General Elections in Gombe State, Nigeria" focused on electoral misconducts reported during Nigeria's 2019 general elections, using Gombe State as reference. Data were collected through primary and secondary sources. The findings revealed that there were electoral misconducts in several areas during the 2019 general elections not only in Gombe Metropolis but in other parts of the State. These misconducts ranged from vote buying, to material inducements and destructions of election materials, among others. The study recommends the need for a new electoral law that will criminalize vote buying and other sundry electoral frauds in future elections in Gombe and other parts of the country. Uchenna (24), in his work "Electoral violence, malpractice and justice system in Nigeria: a Christian critique" examined the trends in election related crimes with a view to recommending biblical principles that will help in mitigating the menace and ensuring electoral justice, free and fair elections in the electoral system in Nigeria. The paper adopted the historical, expository and hermeneutical methods in interpreting the phenomena. It discovers that electoral violence has become deeply rooted in electoral process in Nigeria over the years and that the judicial system has failed to evolve a judicial practice that will ensure electoral offenses are eliminated in Nigeria. The paper recommends the establishment of Electoral Offences Commission to be headed by a religious practitioner, a massive education of the electorate by the Church on election and leadership. Finally offenders of electoral crimes

should be sanctioned by the State for a number of years to serve as deterrent to others within the political space. Aluaigba (25), lamented in the study “Democracy deferred: The effects of electoral malpractice on Nigeria’s path to democratic consolidation” and raised some pertinent questions such as: How do election malpractices affect the quality of Nigeria’s democracy? How do electoral malpractices affect the outcome of elections in Nigeria? Can democracy be consolidated in Nigeria in the face of elections that do not reflect the will of the voters? How can Nigeria chart a credible path towards stabilizing the country’s democracy? This paper presents qualitative data and analyses of the above questions, among others that the conduct of elections in Nigeria since 1999 has been inundated with malpractices in the electioneering process. Furthermore, the trend has worsened with each election, as witnessed in 1999, 2003 and 2007 polls. During these three elections, rigging, violence and intimidation flourished with reckless abandon.

The term electoral mal-practices and violence is not only an organized act of pandemonium, inflicting of physical harm, threat and outright intimidation of electorate as well as political opponents, but should also include activities that are capable of causing psychological and emotional distortion to the electoral process. According to Galtung (26), violence is categorized into psychological, physical and structural. According to him violence can start silently and build up heavy emotions from aggressive negative comments or behaviour. The accumulated emotions are ventilated through disagreement, involving assault, fighting and attacks, intimidation, among others. According to Albert (27), physical violence begins with either mild and or hard assaults in form of physical manifestation of hostility. The psychological violence has to do with a situation where citizens are left under the condition of perpetual state of fear. In this case the citizens are left unprotected as security agencies find it difficult to assure the citizens of their protection within the framework of electoral security [28]. Structural violence is the accumulation of long period of discriminatory politics, ethnic manipulations, religious and regional cleavages. Where exclusivist approach is entrenched in society, the aggrieved may find alternatives means of addressing their dilemma. One of these alternatives is the use of arms as a means of violence in the face of social injustice.

Electoral violence converse by this paper includes the following:

1. Creating atmosphere of threats at the polling unit.
2. The use of smart phone to snap voters while voting to know who they have voted for.
3. Buying of ballot papers and stealing of ballot boxes.

4. Thumb printing of ballot papers and loading of ballot boxes with them.
5. Allocation of purportedly voted figures to a preferred candidate by the power that be without voting.
6. The unscrupulous ineligibility of candidates duly elected
7. Erroneous disqualification of elected candidates with impunity
8. Over bloating of voted figures to voters duly registered.
9. Inconsistencies in the decision of electoral tribunal.
10. Deliberate and lopsided interpretation of electoral rules to disenfranchise certain individuals
11. False declaration of electoral results
12. Inconclusive election sometimes declared by INEC to favour a particular candidate.
13. Deployment of military to form atmosphere of intimidation at voting centres
14. Targeting INEC facilities and election materials,
15. Acting and speaking with heart breaking tones of force and terror, such as “we have even won. Making voters to think why should they waste their time when the vote is not going to count
16. Application of litigations and court injunction to distort elections,
17. Granting opportunity for non-accredited and unregistered persons to vote.
18. Financial and material inducement of election officials and party agent to perpetrate irregularities

According to Nwolise (28), electoral violence is characterized by harassment of opponents of a ruling party by security agents. This act has generated political apathy arisen from the fear by voters as a result of intimidation by thugs and security agents. The announcement of false election results or deliberate delays in announcing election results also constitute electoral violence. Furthermore, the absence of electoral officials, voting materials and electoral result forms from polling booth are also issues of electoral violence. The delay in voting and partisan activities of police and other security agents have made the electorate to lose confidence in the participation and conduct of any election. In addition, electoral malpractices are problematic and are on the rise almost in every election in Nigeria. Given the Nigeria’s context, electoral malpractice is an act regarded as illegal which violate the basic rules of the democratic process. This act is carried out by some electoral officials both ranks and files, political parties and their supporters, candidates, and the electorate. This act negatively impact free, fair, credible and transparent conduct of elections. The irregularities surrounding the electoral process in

Nigeria have compromise legitimacy and instill lack of trust on the electoral process by the electorate.

Therefore, electoral malpractices as further used in this paper include the following:

1. Featuring and the imposition of unqualified candidates
3. Authoritarian selection of candidates
4. Buying of voters' card from prospective electorate at home by some greedy politicians
5. Cancellation of election date for lack of adequate preparedness
6. Lack of accountability for electoral offences
7. Unstructured, disorganized and dysfunctional political parties
8. Deployment of counterfeit ballot papers and influencing of votes
9. Falsifying of voters figures and results during elections
10. Causing artificial scarcity of electoral materials during registration of voters
11. Giving under-age opportunity to vote
12. Using cult members as thugs to intimidate political opponents
13. Inducement of INEC officials and voters financially or promise of political appointment and other corrupt practices
14. Non-fulfillment of party manifestoes
15. Muddling and mutilation of voters' register
16. Deliberate partiality of the electoral body

From the corollary of the above, a lot of people have not come to terms that it is not only when there are obvious and practical shortcomings in the electoral process, that one can frantically say the election is flawed with malpractices. Conversely, there are other latent ways as described above that can absolutely distort the smooth electoral procedures.

Since the return to civilian rule in 1999, and in previous electoral processes dating from 1959, to 2023, have been overwhelmed by assassination, affray, killings, attacks, assault, among others. Nigeria recorded violent attacks, characterized as operation "Wild Wild West" in 1965, following the assembly elections in the South-West. Also during the Second Republic, in 1983, there was post-election violence involving Adekunle Ajasin and Akin Omoboriowo in Ondo State, where lives and property were destroyed [29]. Equally in the recent time, the threat of violence is the biggest challenge as Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC), laments that 242 polling units in 10 Local Government Areas of Katsina State were at risk due to insecurity. INEC has also been a victim of man-induced violence in many parts of the country. In Abeokuta, their eight generating sets were damaged, and over 65,600 Permanent Voters Cards (PVCs), 904 ballot boxes, 57 election bags, and 29 voting cubicles, were destroyed [29]. The 2023 campaign

time and general elections in Nigeria was a season for thugs, fear and disillusionments. The Labour Party, for example, complained the harassment of its supporters in Ebonyi, Nasarawa, Katsina and Lagos States. The Peoples Democratic Party (PDP) protested attacks on its members and supporters in Kaduna, Port Harcourt, Zamfara and Maiduguri. Other political parties also complained been denied the opportunity to paste posters or erect billboards or even gain access to the media by incumbent governors [29].

The increasing violence trailing electioneering campaign across the country was expressed as gunmen killed Victoria Chintex, women leader of the Labour Party (LP), in Kaura, Kaduna State on December 1, 2022 and Christopher Elehu, Labour Party House of Assembly candidate, on 16, December was murdered in Imo State by suspected assassins in Onuimo Local Government Area. Also the convoy of Ikedi Ohakim, a former governor of Imo State, was attacked with several security men killed [30]. Many parties have been denied access to venues for campaigns by the ruling party in some states, and many campaign rallies have been disrupted by hoodlums half way across the country [31]. The violent threat to 2023 general elections can also be seen from Boko Haram in the North East, bandits and jihadists in the North West, and Biafra separatist agitators in the South East. To organize free and fair elections in these volatile areas were difficult. The reason is that insecurity has limited INEC's access to many violent prone zones. The internally displaced people for instance, could not be registered or issue voters' cards in some local government areas in the North West, North Central and North East zones [31]. Since 2021 IPOB has killed several politicians, and parties could not hold their rallies. This has obstructed some registered voters from casting their ballots. Also in Kaduna state, over 200,000 were displaced from 148 towns and villages by gunmen over the past six years, and the displaced people were unable to vote. Areas where herder-farmer, ethnic, religious or other communal tensions and attacks were predominant have scared voters away from casting their ballots [32].

The used of abusive, insulting words during campaigns followed by denial of political party of holding their rally in public places. For instance, Governor Nyesom Wike of Rivers state on 12 October 2022 issued Executive Order 21 compelling political parties to pay N5Million for use of the state public schools and sundry spaces for campaign rallies [33]. According to Opejobi (34), that Wike also shut down Atiku's campaign office in Port Harcourt on December 24 by alleging that the office was cited in Port Harcourt without government's approval. Furthermore, the prevention of opposition parties or individuals to campaign in areas where a political

party or individual is perceived to have its electoral strength is electoral violence. For example, Godwin Obaseki also denied Labour party of using the Ogbemudia stadium for its rally on 11 November 2022 alleging that the notice to use the stadium was received 24 hours to the rally [35]. Unequal opportunities for political parties and candidates deliberate changes in dates, venue of events to the advantages of others. Partisan delimitation of electoral constituencies and location of polling booths, exorbitant fees for the collection of party nomination forms, reliance on vote buying, and force instead of competence. Restraints imposed on voters, the use of incumbency factor to give undue advantage to some candidates has unleashed electoral violence as politicians are desperate to influence the electoral process. In the course of that, the acts associated with violence such as physical harm, verbal intimidation and hate speech were unleashed to non supporters and symbols such as vehicles, polling booths or data [36]. The unhealthy competing for nomination during party primaries among politicians which characterized Edo state Peoples Democratic Party (PDP) on Monday May 22, 2022 led to violent confrontations between supporters [37].

Following the presidential election of 2007, the Chief European Union observer Max Van Den Berg reported that the handling of the polls had fallen far short of basic international standards, citing poor election organization, lack of transparency, significant evidence of fraud, voter disenfranchisement, violence and bias [38]. According to Ashby (39), the election was the worst one had ever seen anywhere in the world, with rampant vote rigging, violence, theft of ballot boxes and intimidation. It was alleged that at one polling station in Yenagoa, in the oil-rich south, where 500 people were registered to vote, more than 2,000 votes were counted [40]. In the case of 2011, there were cases of stuffing of ballot boxes, underage voting and outright falsification of election results reported in some states. In fact with regard to the post-election violence 121 dead in Kaduna 50, Kano 30, Bauchi 16, Kastina 8, Gombe 17 and 15,000 displaced [40]. In 2015 general election there were reports of underage voting and over voting in the North, ballot theft, and vote buying, among others which also did temper on the credibility of the election. In the 2019 general elections, there were reports of electoral malpractices which ranged from violence, intimidation of voters, vote buying and selling, ballot box snatching, militarizing the election, among others [40]. From the forgoing, is it clear that an extensive body of literature exists on electoral-malpractices and violence written by various authorities. But there is, however, no recent systematic academic treatment of the problem of electoral malpractices and violence at the polling stations as threat to the conduct of future

elections in Nigeria. It is this area the paper contributes to exiting body of knowledge.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Studying electoral malpractices and violence in Nigeria is significant as it highlights the challenges to free and fair elections. It also brings to the knowledge of electoral stakeholders that fear of violence and rigging of elections can discourage citizens from participating in the electoral process. The findings will also encourage policymakers and electoral institutions with better legislation and measures to strengthen electoral processes. Studying these issues can help promote peace-building and social unity among inter-party members. With this study, patterns of malpractices and violence can be identified by analyzing past electoral malpractices and violence to avoid the repetition of the same mistakes. It can also contribute to public awareness campaigns about the importance of capacity building, electoral integrity and citizens' rights. From the knowledge of this study, scholars, activists, and policymakers will work towards fostering a more democratic and peaceful future elections in Nigeria.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The study therefore utilized Structural Functionalism theory propounded by Herbert Spencer. He sees structural functionalism as where individuals or institutions carry out specific functions to maintain society [41]. The assumptions of the theory focus on several units of analysis such as society, individual, community, family, organizations, among others. Specifically, these units have requisite functions to maintain peace, order, equilibrium in electoral process. Voters, INEC, political parties, candidates, the security agencies and the judiciary have specific functions to perform in order to ensure violent free elections. The inability of voters, institutions, and electoral relevant bodies to manage and conduct elections effectively has been the cause of electoral malpractices and violence. Structural functionalist expects voters to vote rightly, INEC to perform its functions adequately, political parties to exercise their duties effectively, and the security agencies to provide maximum security to protect lives and property and the judiciary to be independent and discharge its functions of adjudication without bias. From the corollary of the above, INEC officials are expected to organize, undertake and supervise all elections, register political parties, arrange for the annual examination and auditing of the funds and accounts of political parties, conduct the registration of persons qualified to vote, maintain and revise the register of voters for the purpose of any election, monitor political campaigns and provide rules and regulations which shall govern the political parties, conduct voter and civic education; promote knowledge of sound democratic election processes; among others. INEC is also expected to display

openness and transparency in all its activities and in its relationship with all stakeholders. Also expected in the affairs of the INEC are credibility and impartiality to deliver quality electoral services efficiently and effectively, guided by best international practice and standards [40].

Polling agents as well are required to carry out their functions conscientiously to maintain the electoral process. Being appointed by the candidate to observe proceedings on polling day at polling places, need to check the ballot box to ensure is empty before the opening of the poll, assist in detecting any incidences of impersonation, and should not perpetuate behaviour that impede, obstruct or intimidate voters on their way in or out of the polling station. Also the electorate has to vote wisely and shun the collection of money for vote, relegate tribal sentiment and religious consideration, among others to maintain the electoral process. When all these interconnected units adequately carry out their functions threat to future elections will be eliminated.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted secondary research method. This method involves the analysis of secondary data sourced from textbook, Journals, official publications, seminar paper, academic materials, internet and other materials relevant to the study. In other words, this research work is based on qualitative technique used to gather and analyze non-numerical data and experiences from past electoral mal-practices and violence in Nigeria's elections.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

Studying electoral malpractices and violence in Nigeria is fraught with limitations. This is because reliable data on electoral malpractices are inadequate. Also violence are underreported making comprehensive analysis challenging. Media coverage may be biased, influenced by political affiliations, which affects the understanding of the scale and nature of electoral issues.

ELECTORAL MAL-PRACTICES AND VIOLENCE THREAT TO THE CONDUCT OF FUTURE ELECTION IN NIGERIA

Electoral malpractice and violence at the polling station include voter intimidation, vote-buying, ballot stuffing and falsification of election results. This has raised concerns about the credibility and fairness of elections in the country. It has also posed severe threat to the integrity of future elections in Nigeria. Electoral malpractice, violence, threats of violence, among others and their prospects of undermining future elections are glaring and starring on us. Since 1999, 2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019 and 2023, elections in Nigeria have repeatedly demonstrated a consistent and continued pattern of electoral malpractices and violence. This include the killing of

candidates, intimidation of voters, rigging, connivance of electoral officials and the security agencies to favour their preferred candidates and harassment of politicians [42]. Given the above experience, security officers, the police in particular, have always been criticized by national and international observers, for their failure to protect voters. The abuse of human rights and failure to uphold the Law and in some cases direct complicity in election disruption, violence, vote rigging, intimidation and ballot box theft have consistently occurred in every election in Nigeria. The impact of electoral malpractices has been noted to contribute to insecurity which has in turn hinder development with the prevalence of poverty, insecurity and unemployment [43]. The country is grappling with poverty, with more than 67.3% of its citizens living in abject poverty leading to a trade-off of votes to undermine the integrity of the electoral process [44]. Electoral malpractice has a high propensity of orchestrating violence, leading to a retrogressive effect on the development of the country. It is clearly observed that the proliferation of small arms to advance electoral malpractice poses a security risk to the electorate, INEC officials and candidates.

Electoral mal-practices have economic implications given the costs associated with the management of elections which are usually huge burden on candidates. Arises from the huge financial resources needed to sponsor an election, the process automatically becomes a do or die affairs. In this context further time and resources are deployed to the employment of firearms and recruitment of thugs to facilitate mayhem, destroy election materials and infrastructure with various negative economic and developmental consequences [45]. Electoral malpractices and violence have caused several threats to the democratic stability in Nigeria. This is because they have potential of truncating democratic stability in a country like what happened to the First, Second and Third republic which returned the military to power. Anything that undermines the political process and stability of a nation can be regarded as threat. When a political system is not conducive for investors and business to thrive and as a result of electoral violence the economy is always taken backward. The backwardness will always manifest a decline of gross domestic product; increase unemployment and drastically reduced the amount of buying and selling in the state. Since independence, Nigeria's democratization process had witnessed massive electoral mal-practices and violence which have undermined the very ethics of liberal democracy [7]. In Nigeria, the concept of democracy has become difficult to define and this is because the very factor which qualifies a democratic government has been difficult to achieve. Elections are central to the existence, stability and development of democracies

and political parties. This is evident, because a free and fair election promotes and ensures democracy. Taking a look at the democratic history of Nigeria, it is observed that electoral violence has adversely affected the country to the extent of causing major political upheavals and the termination of democracy [7]. It has also served the ignorable purposes of weakening the people's confidence and support for democratic institution in Nigeria. This has weakened the development programs and the pillar of democracy in Nigeria. Electoral manipulation and violence have truncated the popular mandate and wishes of the people. In the history of Nigeria, the 2007 general election has been described as the worst election ever conducted and has made it difficult in strengthening the worth of democracy [7].

Electoral mal-practices and violence are major challenges to democratic process in Nigeria. This is because sometimes votes are subverted against the popular candidate for the interest of few elites. This has further discouraged a lot of interested and qualified men and women in participating in any elections [7]. In Nigeria, candidates are sometimes rigged out from winning an election even though they had the votes and support of the people. Consequently, election riggings at the polling stations have aided the violation of the fundamental human rights which is the right to life for every citizen born in a country. Nigerian elections are constitutionally intended to promote stabilized government from the people's consent. The contrary is the case as the stability and peaceful environment required for the success of democracy have been severely endangered leading to high rate of political apathy.

Adekanye cited in Ugwuala; Kalu and Elechi (7), opines that the quest to win election by all means is associated with political tension; crisis and even violence which have claimed both candidates and electorate with a bid to control the government. This situation is more worrisome as some electoral officials entrusted to conduct a free and fair election have become biased making unpopular candidates to emerge victorious in elections. Kurfi (46), has observed, rigging in an election is as old as Nigeria. With that, the democratic aspirations of citizen have faded away as votes do not count. Electoral malpractice and violence have general negative effect on Nigeria's democratic future because the trend is increasing instead of reducing. The trends have actually undermined the chances of successful elections and consolidation of democracy in Nigeria. Electoral malpractice has enhanced the enthronement of leaders that lack accountability, integrity and responsibility in various levels of public offices in Nigeria. This has affected the quality of leadership and governance in our nation. As a result, Nigeria is still battling with the challenges of bad leadership, poor governance and corruption. These issues have

adversely affected social transformation, economic advancement and national development.

Furthermore, electoral malpractice leads to violence, chaos, anarchy and unrest. This has been the trend in most of our elections since 1999. As a result, several people have lost their lives and valuable property has been destroyed. In most cases, the perpetrators of these heinous crimes are neither brought to book nor made to face the wrath of the law. Human Rights Watch (47) estimates that a minimum of 300 Nigerians were killed during the April 2007 elections. Prior to the elections, political assassinations, bombings, and deadly clashes were recorded between rival gangs organized by politicians and parties that claimed at least one hundred lives. Voter turnout during the 2007 elections was very low across the country as fear of violence discouraged many Nigerians from coming out to vote. Human Rights Watch interviewed quite a number of eligible voters indicated their intention not to vote. One retiree in the town of Oye Ekiti told Human Rights Watch that the elderly citizens (both men and women) were scared to participate in the election [47]; [48],[49]. Politically motivated violence resulting in assassinations and other election related killings have been associated with the Nigerian democratic project since 1999 [50]. A large number of Nigerians have lost their lives and many others displaced with property worth billions of naira destroyed. These have resulted in political climate of hostility, instability and uncertainty. Intra and inter party conflicts directly and indirectly related to power struggles have degenerated into party indiscipline, lawlessness with patron and client relationships dictating who stands for or wins elective position [51]. Over the years it is observed that the political system is producing non-democratic power which diminish trust and undermines the quality of democracy directly by killing voters, candidates, and limiting inclusive participation [52]. Consequently this has led to violent contention between opposing parties thereby posing serious challenges to the consolidation of democracy in future elections in Nigeria.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, electoral mal-practices and violence in this paper is used as not only the presence of organized act of chaos, but also with the presence of other restrained actions against opponents, electorate and the entire electoral process. For instance, the denial of political opponents of the opportunity to utilize public places for campaigns and rallies are one and the same to electoral violence and mal-practices. This most times resulted in political apathy as experienced in September 21, 2024 gubernatorial elections in Edo state. The biggest threat to general elections in future is the threat of violence as politicians are doing everything possible above their limits to grab power by all means. This is because

politicians see election as a do or die affair with the full support of their party gladiators. This action undermined government institutions saddled with the responsibilities to ensure free and fair elections. From the past elections, the application of violence and malpractices has been the sources of political victory. Given the upcoming 2027 general elections, political assassinations, killings, denial of public places for political campaigns and rallies, buying of voters' cards, among others are prominently going to take the centre stage in Nigeria. It is against this backdrop that some recommendations are made.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The Bimodal Voters Accreditation System and other sensitive materials should be monitored by everybody around the polling booths to prevent rigging and other forms of electoral manipulations. There should be strong advocacy groups to instill confidence in the electorate, and the electorate should be educated on the voting procedure, to reflect their voting rights and to understand the dangers of political apathy and electoral malpractices. The Electoral Commission should be independent and be firm to its decision of making the elections free. Strict penalty should be meted on electoral offenders to serve as a deterrent to election violators. The connivance of some electoral officials with some party agents to discourage voters or to tamper with the election results should not be allowed to take place in future elections. The unfairness and injustice demonstrated by the electoral officials in the past elections should be avoided in the upcoming 2027, because of the post election violence emanating from the act. The Nigeria Police Force and other related agencies should be strengthened with moral and logistics supports to curtail electoral violence and malpractices at the polling centers. Also the Electoral Tribunal personnel should be trained to accurately interpret the constitution as it affects election. The dissemination of false political information on campaign and rally places should be eliminated. Politicians should focus on issues-based rather than attacking their opponents with hate speeches. All political candidates and their supporters should uphold the principles of tolerance, respect, political engagements in the upcoming 2027 general elections. Incumbent governors should provide enabling environment for their opponents to exercise their political rights. The use of thugs to dehumanize oppositions should be checked by the security agents to instill confidence in the electorate to exercise their franchise. The constitutional or electoral offences court should be set up to try and punish perpetrators of election malpractices and violence. In addition, the legislature should strengthen the provisions relating to malpractices and violence in the Electoral Act in order to punish those who breach the law whether they are agents or principal actors without favoring any political party, religious, ethnic or any other biases. Finally adequate attention should be paid to

capacity building where stakeholders will be taught the basics of electoral processes.

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